

the F_1 , 275 panicles of the F_2).

The F_1 population, with a wide range of variation (mean 76% Pb, 75% Sb), markedly exceeded the high parent (56%). The F_2 population had a continuous distribution—10-90% Pb and 20- to 90% Sb, mean of 60% Pb and 59% Sb. The curve was unimodal, but skewed somewhat negatively (see figure). Only a few plants exceeded the lower parental limit and 20% exceeded the upper limit of IR30, indicating that multiple genes with opposite effects were operating.

The dominance effect (Pb - 34.0, Sb - 34.2) was 2-3 times higher than the additive effects (Pb - 16.4, Sb - 12.0). The potence ratio was more than 2 (Pb - 2.16, Sb - 2.60), indicating over-dominance of genes governing this trait. The effective factor pairs estimate was

Distribution and means of parents, F_1 , and F_2 plants of IR30/IR32385-37-3-3-3 cross, by high density grain index. IRRI, 1987 wet season.

0.58 for Pb and 1.26 for Sb, indicating that the trait is controlled by a few genes of the polymeric model. The degree of heterosis was 86.76 (Pb), 69.96 (Sb); heterobeltiosis was 33.22 (Pb) and 33.92 (Sb).

The heritability estimate was very high, more than 80%. Thus, selections for more high density grain may be effective in early segregating generations such as F_3 or F_4 . We have selected 40 F_3 lines to evaluate in the F_4 . □

Yield potential

Performance of new Bw rice varieties compared to Bg 400-1 in Sri Lanka

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Bg 400-1 (Ob 678//IR20/H4), bred at Central Rice Breeding Centre, Batalagoda, Sri Lanka, is a very popular 4- to 4 1/2-mo variety because it adapts to diverse environments. Under good management, it has produced 7 t/ha in the low country wet zone of Sri Lanka.

However, panicle sterility, particularly in the yala season (Apr-Aug), has drastically reduced yields. To find a replacement for Bg 400-1, we evaluated lines in yala 1986 (Apr-Aug) and maha 1986/87 (Sep-Mar) in farmers' fields.

Bw 295-5 (Ob 678/Bw 254-1) and sister lines Bw 271-1 and Bw 271-2 (Bw 259-4/Bw 100) were chosen for field testing and comparison with Bg 400-1.

Trial sites represented the varying production potentials of diverse soil conditions in the low country wet zone.

Rice was wet seeded at 100 kg/ha in plots 6 × 4.5 m, with 30 cm space between plots.

Fertilizer and agrochemicals were applied as recommended in farmer-managed trials guided by field staff. Plot yields were converted to t/ha at 14% moisture level.

Average yields of the four varieties did not differ significantly. However, yields varied greatly within and across environments (13 locations in yala and 18 in maha), partly because of differing

soil fertility and farmer management levels.

Regression analysis showed that Bw 295-5 is as well adapted to a range of environments as is Bg 400-1. Bw 295-5 is similar to Bg 400-1 in plant height, tiller number, panicle length, grain color, and grain size.

Results show Bw 295-5 should be favorably considered. It is better than Bw 271-1 and Bw 271-2 in areas where Bg 400-1 is currently grown. □

Breeding methods

Substituting urea and boric acid for gibberellic acid in hybrid rice seed production

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The growth regulator gibberellic acid (GA_3) is used in hybrid rice seed production in China to increase panicle exertion, stigma exertion, and plant height and to synchronize flowering between primary and secondary tillers.

That helps increase outcrossing on the male sterile line and hybrid seed yield. But GA_3 is expensive (\$8/20 g) in countries outside China. When applied at 30-45 g/ha, costs soar. GA_3 also increases plant height, which induces lodging. The extra exerted panicles can break during the wet season (WS) under torrential rains and strong winds.

We looked for a suitable substitute for GA_3 . Hybrid seed production experiments with sorghum and pearl millet have shown the effectiveness of urea and boric acid sprays in increasing hybrid seed yields. These chemicals are available and cheap throughout the

Table 1. Effect of urea, boric acid, and GA₃ sprays at various stages on seed yield of CMS rice line IR54752A. IRRRI, 1987 WS.

Chemical and concentration	Seed yield (kg/ha) with spraying at			
	Full booting	Initial heading	20% heading	Mean seed yield (kg/ha)
Control (no spray)	376	381	443	400
GA ₃ 30 ppm	380	386	487	418
GA ₃ 60 ppm	370	421	501	431
Boric acid 0.5%	334	353	497	395
Boric acid 1.0%	391	347	491	410
Urea 1.0%	394	436	495	442
Urea 1.5%	397	457	536	463
Mean	377	397	493	
CV (%)	16.6			

Table 2. Effect of urea, boric acid, KNO₃, and GA₃ sprays at various growth stages on seed yield of CMS rice line IR54752A. IRRRI, 1988 DS.

Chemical and concentration	Seed yield (kg/ha) with spraying at			
	Full booting	Initial heading	20% heading	Mean seed yield (kg/ha)
Control	478	472	392	447
GA ₃ (90 ppm)	562	570	452	528
Urea (2%)	621	511	565	566
Boric Acid (1.5%)	625	500	534	553
KNO ₃ (2%)	577	509	431	506
Mean	572	512	475	—
CV (%)	7.7			

Paired comparisons

	LSD	
	1%	5%
1. Between main plot means (averaged over all subplot treatments)	127.37	55.22
2. Between subplot means (averaged over all main plot treatments)	69.88	49.84
3. Between subplot means at the same main plot treatment	121.03	86.33

world. We tested their efficacy in hybrid rice seed production.

Field experiments in 1987-88 at IRRRI involved various concentrations and times of application of urea, boric acid KNO₃, and GA₃ on CMS line IR54752A and its maintainer IR54752B planted at a female:male row ratio of 8:2 in a 10.8-m² plot. The experiments were in a split-plot design with growth stages as main plot and chemical treatments as subplots, with three replications.

In the 1987 WS experiment, seed yields of treated and control plots were not significantly different (Table 1). In

1988 dry season (DS), 2% KNO₃ was tested with selected concentrations of GA₃, urea, and boric acid. Seed yields of IR54752A significantly differed (Table 2). When sprayed at full booting, boric acid (1.5%) gave the highest yield (625 kg/ha) of the CMS line, followed by urea (2%) spray (621 kg/ha). When sprayed at initial heading, GA₃ (90 ppm) gave the highest seed yield (570 kg/ha). Urea (2%) (565 kg/ha) and boric acid (1.5%) (534 kg/ha) sprays at 20% heading gave significantly higher seed yields. On the whole, urea (1.5 to 2.0%) or boric acid (1.5%) sprayed at full

booting, initial heading, or 20% heading was as effective as GA₃. Neither urea nor boric acid increased plant height of either CMS or maintainer lines.

Urea, boric acid, and GA₃ application gave seed sets of 10.7, 9.3, and 11.0%, respectively, compared with 7.7% for control during the DS experiment. It appears that increased seed yields due to application of growth chemicals in DS were due to increased seed set. Even though chemical application increased seed set in WS, seed yield was not increased significantly, indicating a negative effect of some other factor.

The overall results indicate that 1.5-2% urea or 1.5% boric acid can substitute for GA₃ in hybrid rice seed production. □

Expression and segregation of isozyme genes in rice microspore-derived calli

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Whether anther culture (AC) derivatives represent a random gametic array of the microspore pool is of primary importance in applying this methodology to rice breeding. To test the randomness of in vitro induction, we studied segregations of heterozygous markers among AC derivatives.

Table 1. Isozyme genes expressed in the microspore-derived callus of rice.^a IRRRI, 1988.

<i>Adh-1</i>	<i>Amp-1</i>
<i>Sdh-1</i>	<i>Amp-2</i>
<i>Icd-1</i>	<i>Amp-3</i>
<i>Cat-1</i>	<i>Amp-4</i>
<i>Pgi-1</i>	<i>Acp-1</i>
<i>Pgi-2</i>	<i>Acp-2</i>
<i>Pgd-1</i>	<i>Acp-3</i>
<i>Pgd-2</i>	<i>Acp-4</i>
<i>Got-1</i>	<i>Est-1</i>
<i>Got-2</i>	<i>Est-2</i>
<i>Mal-1</i>	<i>Est-9</i>

^a *Pox-2* and *Est-7* never appeared and *Est-5* showed an altered expression in our experiments. Data recorded on the following varieties and crosses: Taipei 309, Aus 454, Fujiminori, Tetep, Dinorado/BR319-1, UPLRi-5/CNA4121, IRAT177/Apura.